

Obesity: an evolutionary view

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Plain Language Summary

Human diet has been modified since we evolved and many studies have attempted to determine an optimum diet derived from fossil evidence. Taking a deeper evolutionary view, it is clear that most mammals have a basic diet of hard-to-digest carbohydrates (fibre), not one focusing on sugars and starches as in modern human diets. A few exceptions occur, such as animals specialising in fruit eating, and carnivores. This insight suggests that the modern obesity epidemic is related to a diet absorbed primarily as glucose. This stimulates a strong insulin response, leading to over-eating and deposition of fat around the body. Thus like most mammals, our bodies are still adapted to eat a diet rich in **fermentable carbohydrate**, rather than in readily-absorbed sugars and starches. However, our relatively small gut volume for our size indicates we also need a high-calorie component, achievable primarily from **saturated fats**.

Abstract

*We need to think about food preparation and ingestion separately from actual nutrient absorption, in order to gain insights into the causes of the modern obesity epidemic. An evolutionary view demonstrates that most mammals **absorb** calories as saturated fats and ketones, with minimal absorption of glucose, although they **ingest** primarily carbohydrates (dietary fibre). Fermenting bacteria use these ingested carbohydrates for their own metabolism, excreting short-chain fatty acids that are then absorbed by gut epithelial cells for their own needs or converted to ketones for distribution more widely in the body. Human gut morphology is broadly similar to that of the other great apes, but has differences indicating a reliance on the consumption of high-quality foods, i.e. containing a high proportion of readily-absorbed nutrients relative to volume. This is achieved by selection as well as by pre-ingestion food preparation. The modern human reliance on most calorie supply from readily digested carbohydrates for absorption as glucose is too recent to show any evolutionarily relevant adaptations.*

What is the problem?

The increasing incidence of obesity and diabetes has become of major concern during the latter half of the last century and to date, as the proportion of populations exhibiting these has grown (Crawford 2002, Slyper 2004, Swinburn et al. 2011, van Raalte & Verchere 2017, Maffetone & Laursen 2020, Mundi et al. 2021, Lustig et al. 2022). Pathologies associated with these conditions include numerous general health complaints, commonly associated with macrovascular (cardiovascular

disease, angina, stroke) and microvascular (retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy) complications (Atkinson et al. 2014, Leighton et al. 2017).

There is a common view that weight gain is simply the result of a calorie¹ intake to expenditure imbalance, thus a low-fat diet or “eat less/move more” approach should resolve it. However, while weight loss following these principles is undoubtedly successful, there is often a disappointing subsequent weight regain (Langeveld & DeVries 2015).

Another tactic is to focus on insulin activity, especially by restricting carbohydrate consumption. A famous example is the 19th century tract “Letter on corpulence” (Banting 1864), but more recently ketogenic and related diets (Volek et al. 2002, Ludwig et al. 2021), based on the underlying mechanism called the insulin/carbohydrate model (Taubes 2013, Astley et al. 2018, Ludwig & Ebbeling 2018, Shimy et al. 2020, Ludwig et al. 2021). This approach remains controversial in spite of reported long-term success (Volek et al. 2011, Fung 2016, Kelly et al. 2020).

Several evolutionary explanations for obesity have been proposed. These explicitly or implicitly indicate a genetic origin (Lev-Ran 2001, Lindeberg 2009, Speakman 2013, Hochberg 2018). However, there is an inconsistency between genetic change, since at a population level it is not as swift as the recent propensity to obesity. It can also lead to a fatalistic assumption counterproductive to any opportunities to manage or reverse obesity since “It’s in my genes. I can’t do anything about that.”

Other approaches have focused on surveying the prevalence and actions of specific human genes, use of fossil evidence to determine food consumption patterns, or using modern hunter/gatherer societies as a proxy for our recent and ancient ancestors.

I consider firstly a specific gene function aspect, commonly referred to as a “thrifty gene” or obesity genes. Secondly I discuss human diets from anthropological studies, and finally I note similarities and differences between human gut structure and function to that of our closest great ape relatives and mammals more generally.

Genetic explanations

The “thrifty gene” concept considers a genetic adaptation initially providing specific survival advantages, but now maladaptive (Neel 1962). Speakman (2013) expanded this into three broad categories of possible function:

1. that the ability to develop obesity is adaptive in a seasonally variable food supply,
2. that obesity was not favourable and seldom encountered in the evolutionary past, but is now maladaptive and driven by some other favourable trait,
3. that mutations favouring obesity are under no to minimal selective pressure, thus possibly answering the observation that some individuals in a population are prone to obesity and some apparently not.

Neel (1962) proposed that diabetes indicates a “thrifty” genotype gone wrong in the modern era. In particular, that diabetes of later (post-reproductive) ages is often associated with increased body

¹ Calorie is being used here in the commonly used sense, rather than Calories, kilocalories or kilojoules, the terms preferred in modern metabolic studies (Hargrove 2007).

weight and specifically a diet involving increased stimulation of insulin release, now normally recognised as the T2D² form of diabetes. However, a more recent review found no evidence for global selection for T2D risk, and evidence of risk did not indicate a "thrifty gene" response. This included prevalence of T2D risk/protective genes across African, European and east Asian populations (Ayub et al. 2014).

T1D² is an autoimmune disease and commonly early onset. There is a strong genetic component, with no association for longevity but rather an "impaired reproductive performance" (Neel 1962) and thus it does not contribute to a "thrifty" phenotype. The propensity for diabetes of any type to reflect a "thrifty" genotype could be considered under Speakman's first point, but it appears that diabetes of any form is more likely to be detrimental at any stage. Further, since Neel's speculation in 1962, the incidence of T2D is now prevalent in childhood, and at an increasing rate (Dabelea et al. 2014, Buttermore et al. 2021).

A survey of a wide range of gene variations previously associated with obesity failed to find evidence of positive selection pressure in favour of obesity development. From this obesity/genetic view, the authors concluded there is currently no confirmed support for a "thrifty gene" concept (Wang & Speakman 2016). A genetic background for obesity has also been discarded in favour of an environmental "obesogen hypothesis" (Baillie-Hamilton 2002).

Variation in the number of salivary amylase gene (AMY1) copies, compared across human populations with habitual diets varying in starch contribution, suggests increased copy number is a positive reaction to a higher starch-content diet (Perry et al. 2007). They speculated that the evolutionary advantage arises as quicker starch conversion to glucose could be lifesaving under extreme diarrhoeal disease conditions. Whilst improved postprandial glycaemic response to starch ingestion is associated with increased copy number (Mandel & Breslin 2012), low copy number tends to be associated with increased obesity, insulin resistance and diabetes (Elder et al. 2018) that could be argued to be consistent with the existence of a "thrifty gene". However, other data fail to find such an association (Usher et al. 2015). Although commonly regarded as assisting in converting ingested starches to glucose, this enzyme in practice is of little importance (Fernández & Wiley 2017). In a comparison with the related great apes, salivary amylase production is more likely to correlate with tannin content of diets (Behringer et al. 2013). The potential for AMY1 copy number variation to represent a "thrifty gene" concept remains undecided.

Human evolution and dietary evidence

Ancestral diets from archaeology and anthropology

What is the human ancestral diet? Many attempts have been made to define this, resolving to some fairly different insights into the value and importance of calories derived from carbohydrate, fat and 2 T1D and T2D refers to diabetes types one and two as the most common forms. T1D is generally recognised as an autoimmune disease with strong genetic components, while T2D is more a metabolic response or dysfunction associated with diet (Poretsky 2017). Previously commonly referred to as juvenile or insulin-dependent and adult or noninsulin-dependent, respectively.

protein. Archaeological and anthropological resources are key components for these investigations. Often acknowledged is the difficulty in extrapolating macronutrient ratios from minimal evidence, and this is true even in descriptions of modern hunter/gatherer societies (Crittenden & Schnorr 2017).

Modern hunter/gatherer diets may be indicative of ancestral human diets. In some cases plants are estimated to provide as much as 65% of calories, while in other circumstances animals/fish dominate, for example in circumpolar regions or equestrian cultures (reviewed in Crittenden & Schnorr 2017).

Thus clearly humans have adapted to remarkably wide food choices. What is noticeable is the emphasis often placed on at least some animal/fish foods in traditional cultures across the world (Price 1939), with essential fatty acids, micronutrients and high quality proteins being prized components (Milton 2003). However, these are **modern** humans eating these foods and therefore can provide little evolutionary depth, other than that the introduction of “modern” foods is often noted to be detrimental to health (Price 1939). In this context, “modern” foods are essentially an increase in calorie supply from readily-digested sugars and starches.

Archaeological studies and hypotheses provide plenty of speculation about early human species’ diets. Even more difficult, with only fossil and cultural artefacts as a guide, is determination of the proportion, daily or seasonal, that various foods might have made to calorie supply. In spite of these uncertainties, proponents for emulating a supposed Paleolithic diet claim health benefits (Eaton & Eaton III 2000, de la O et al. 2021), but also that the “Paleo” diets are “myths of a lost golden age and utopian manuals” (Johnson 2015).

Preparation of starchy foods, in particular cereal grains, is evident from archaeological investigations. For example, starchy roots or tubers are evident from the Klasies River Cave up to 120 kya (Larbey et al. 2019). The advent of cereal farming, generally considered to have developed from about 11 kya, also provides evidence within the last few thousand years of grain processing, such as grinding, cooking and brewing (Heron et al. 2016, Valamoti et al. 2021). Alcohol, from brewing processes, is higher in calories than glucose, is readily absorbed through mass flow absorption, and the brewing process itself provides some extra vitamin content, especially B vitamins from yeasts. In addition, alcohol itself is pleasurable to humans, and other animals (Morris et al. 2006).

Additional evidence of a change to simple carbohydrate addition to human diets can be derived from teeth. For example, Neanderthals show evidence of starchy plant material trapped in tooth calculus (Henry et al. 2011). Hominin fossils generally reflect intact dentition through the Pliocene (generally 5.3 – 2.5 mya), while tooth loss starts becoming evident during the Pleistocene (2.5 mya – 11.7 kya) and into the Holocene (11.7 kya to the present), reflecting increased reliance on carbohydrate calories, as well as development of food processing techniques allowing adults with severe tooth loss to survive (Scott & Turner 1988). Incidence of dental caries provides good evidence of long-term carbohydrate consumption, with some interesting relatively recent historical diet changes providing stark examples of changes in caries incidence (Price 1939, Tikhonov et al. 2019). Caries is also noted to be the most prevalent chronic disease of people worldwide, and individuals are susceptible throughout their lifetime (Selwitz et al. 2007). It is therefore evident that starch and fruit

consumption has occurred for at least some hundreds of thousands of years. However, unlike other mammals specialising in calories from carbohydrates (fruit, nectar etc diets), humans show no widespread or strongly selective genetic adaptations to increased readily digestible carbohydrate consumption (Inchley et al. 2016).

Animals-as-food is commonly reported, including cooking and butchering evidence, but within a context of dominance of plant-sourced calories such as fruit, nuts or starchy tubers (Wrangham et al. 1999, Milton 2003, Carmody et al. 2016), with some suggestion that these readily digestible carbohydrates were the calorie source required for brain development through the Pleistocene (Hardy et al. 2015). A largely animal-focused diet (Straus et al. 2015) can induce serious health problems, from hyperinsulinæmic nausea to death, when protein provides greater than about 30% of calories in the diet (Bilsborough & Mann 2006, Tushingham et al. 2021). However, a high supply of calories from animal fat (Ben-Dor et al. 2011, Ben-Dor & Barkai 2021) overcomes the excess protein and need for calories conundrum, although there is also a view that fat would be rare in early human diets (Power & Schulkin 2009).

Previous hominin species' diets can only be inferred from the very few and limited artefacts and fossils. This is equally problematic with modern human diets, because it is not possible to determine the proportion of various diet components. In particular, it is likely that foods only seasonally available may be overemphasised, based on tooth observations or food processing evidence.

Ancestral diets by gut function and structure

Another evolutionary angle is to review mammal gut structure and functions in relation to their habitual diets. In particular, since there are some general principles that these indicate specific diet/gut adaptations (Elgar & Harvey 1987), we can also compare humans with closely-related species to determine ancient genetic signals from diet specialisations.

Function

The vast majority of adult mammals practise a vegetarian diet, either wholly or very largely comprised of plant material. Of these, a common feature is a reliance on leaves for the bulk of their calories. Many also use various combinations of plant parts, often seasonally available components such as fruit and nuts, plus relatively small components of other food sources such as fungi, seaweeds, insects and occasional small animals or eggs. A few specialise in less common items, the most notable being carnivores and frugivores. Apart from carnivores, calorie-seeking behaviour requires investment of effort across a large part of each day. Plant-eaters relying primarily on fermentation of limited-digestibility carbohydrates can be seen to exhibit more complex gastrointestinal structures (McGrosky et al. 2019).

Plant materials comprise various degrees of readily digested carbohydrates, with relatively small amounts of lipids and proteins. A few specific plant parts are richer in fats, such as oily fruit or fatty seeds, but these generally comprise a small proportion of dietary calories of vegetarian mammals. However, by far the bulk of calories present in plant leaves exists as indigestible carbohydrates such as celluloses and pectins. Co-opting bacterial fermentation processes to release these calories is

essentially universal in mammals, and generally present in the gut components *after* the small intestine. Many mammals exhibit remarkable gut adaptations, but all have at least some ability for fermentation in the large intestine. The caloric end point of this bacterial fermentation is SCFA³, (Cummings 1981, McNeil 1984, Bugaut 1987, Mortensen & Clausen 1996, Gibson et al. 1996, Roy et al. 2006). Some examples of major adaptations to this otherwise indigestible diet occur in many animals, but especially notable, for example in horses, pigs, rabbits and ruminants. Even carnivores are now known to exhibit some fermentation ability, especially of difficult-to-digest proteins such as cartilage (Depauw et al. 2013, Butowski et al. 2022).

Structure

A useful overview of animal allometry in respect to gut sizes and structures in relation to the size of the animal may be instructive (Chivers & Hladik 1980, Van Soest 1996). In broad terms, animals with a dietary focus on insects/animal foods have simple globular stomachs, longish small intestines and shorter large intestines. Animals with a focus on plant foods, by far the majority, sometimes have very complex stomachs, and various arrangements for fermentation, with cæcum and large intestine as fermentation chambers.

Non-human primate studies also provide considerable insight, especially those of our closest relatives, the great apes, and particularly the African genera of *Pan* (chimpanzee) and *Gorilla* (Lambert 1998, Hohmann 2009). Apart from humans, great apes derive the bulk of their calories from plant sources, mainly leaves, with some fruit and nuts, but not tubers or grasses (Milton 1987, 1999b). Chimpanzees also supplement with insects and hunt small animals. In terms of gut retention (or transit) time, at 26 hours humans are intermediate between the partially omnivore chimpanzees (23) and the nearly entirely folivore gorillas (37) (Lambert 1998). However, transit time can be quite variable, depending on the bulk volume, especially fibre, of the diet (Milton & Demment 1988).

A noticeable difference between humans and the other great apes is that the volume of total gut represented by small intestine (~50%) and colon (~20%) is approximately the other way round in the apes (Milton 1987). This suggests adaptation to a diet comprised of largely calorie-dense and readily digested components absorbed by stomach and small intestine, and a far smaller proportion of calories associated with fermentation processes (Milton 1999b).

Gorillas acquire more than 50% of their calories from SCFAs produced during fermentation (Popovich et al. 1997). Chimpanzees, like gorillas, consume primarily leafy plant materials, very low in fats and rich in fermentable carbohydrates, but with a higher proportion of digestible carbohydrate from fruit (Conklin-Brittain et al. 2002). The natural great ape diets, as for most primates, provide dietary fats at less than 20% of calories but close to 1:1 ratio of saturated:unsaturated (Milton 1999b). However, these fermentation-sourced fats mean that absorption, rather than direct consumption, is heavily weighted to saturated fats and well above 50% of total calories. In effect, these animals predominantly absorb calories as **saturated fats**.

³ Short-Chain Fatty Acid, typically the saturated fatty acids acetic, propionic and butyric acids.

Humans have been estimated to obtain 5 to 10% of calories from fermentation products (McNeil 1984, Bugaut 1987). Humans thus absorb far fewer calories as SCFAs than the other great apes, but their role in colonic and other health aspects probably outweighs their calorie provision (Wong et al. 2006, Roy et al. 2006, Sonnenburg & Sonnenburg 2014, Blaak et al. 2020, Nogal et al. 2021, Kong et al. 2021).

The relatively small cæcum+colon volume in humans suggests limited opportunity to ferment the more difficult fibrous material that gorillas eat. The great apes focus on dicotyledonous plant materials, primarily with hemicellulose and cellulose content, rather than the more lignified fibres common in grass leaves, common in ruminant and horse diets (Milton 1999b). Fibre in common vegetables, such as cabbage and carrot, is readily fermented in the human gut, while the more difficult fibres of pulses and highly lignified bran from cereals provide bulk and sometimes unfortunate intestinal upset.

In general then, humans exhibit a gut structure suggesting a move away from the more common great ape caloric-reliance on fermentation of otherwise indigestible carbohydrates (fibre) towards a far more readily-digested food. In particular, this is indicated by the unusually long small intestine, reflecting adaptation for a greater component of readily digested and absorbed nutrients (Milton & Demment 1988). Humans thus exhibit considerable gastrointestinal flexibility, processing a wide variety of food sources, including fermentable dietary fibre, but requiring an otherwise far more calorically high-quality food intake. In many respects, this is achieved by extensive pre-consumption processing, especially removal of harder components, e.g. bran of cereals, and making it easier to consume and digest through milling, chopping, moistening and cooking. Preparation to combine various foods from very different sources, for example starches with fats, provides particularly calorie-dense, readily digested foods. Thus humans are purposely preparing foods to be more calorie-dense relative to volume. This is more readily digested and absorbed to support a large body, active lifestyle and large brain. In effect, parts of the gut structure have been replaced by these processes.

Another aspect of readily digested nutrients is the role of animal food products in the human diet. Certainly, animals-as-food provide considerable very readily-digested protein and other nutrients (Milton 1999a). Indeed, many populations have subsisted on a very high proportion of animal products (Price 1939). Further, fossil evidence pre 12 kya suggests a predominantly animal diet (Straus et al. 2015) and potentially with a specific focus on animals as a fat source (Ben-Dor et al. 2011, Ben-Dor 2013), especially in the more temperate regions where dicotyledonous leaf and fruit material would be seasonally short or absent (Ben-Dor et al. 2021). The modern preference for combined fat **with** carbohydrate rather than fat **or** carbohydrate foods, provides a high food reward (DiFeliceantonio et al. 2018). Further, these authors demonstrated that humans estimated the energy content of fats alone far better than of carbohydrates or of carbohydrates combined with fat. The specific mechanism for this is indicated by sensing of the C18:0 saturated fat stearic acid (Senyilmaz-Tiebe et al. 2018) and high satiation commonly reported on high fat/ketogenic diets (Malhotra et al. 2015, Kelly et al. 2020).

Discussion

Gut allometry studies have clearly indicated that we can make some strong associations between gut length or volume relative to body size, and thus a broad definition of an associated diet and lifestyle. Animals with similar lifestyles and diet strategies require bigger digestive organs to support their larger size. Big animals in turn also require more food and thus tend towards more difficult-to-digest foods to provide adequate calories, while small animals require much more specialised diets.

Within the four great ape genera, humans stand out as having “broken the allometry trap”. Specifically, we are relatively large apes with surprisingly small overall gut systems. This suggests a diet rich in nutrients that are readily digested and absorbed. Two specific modifications to our gut structure and function stand out. First is the extraordinarily long small intestine relative to total gut length, thus indicating an emphasis on nutrient absorption. The other is the very low pH of our stomachs (Wrangham et al. 1999, Beasley et al. 2015), suggesting far less emphasis on the microbially-benign plant diets of the other apes. However, there are remarkably few gut function or structural differences between humans and the other great apes (Milton 2003).

Gorillas may derive 50% of their calories from fermentation end products, but even the reduced large intestine still allows humans to derive at least 10% of calories from this source. The small intestine of humans, although functionally similar, is considerably longer than that of the other great apes.

Selection of readily-digested and absorbed foods is clearly important, with seasonally available fruits, nuts and tubers as an important source of calories in the lead up to winter. However, prior to the advent of crop farming with resulting large surpluses of readily storable foods, especially cereals, some other means of supporting the population was required. Animals-for-food remained an obvious answer, although care had to be taken to avoid protein poisoning from an excess of proteins in the diet (Bilsborough & Mann 2006, Tushingham et al. 2021). These proteins are one source of calories, but fat is another major source, both of which are readily digested and absorbed by an acidic stomach and long small intestine.

Human gut structure and size clearly indicate that our active lifestyle and body size cannot be supported by the same diet as other great apes. This means humans need to eat the saturated fats rather than rely on fermentation to provide them. The dominant available sources for humans are C16:0 and C18:0 saturated fats from animal fat. In a few cases, monounsaturated fats, such as avocado, cacao, coconut and olives, can play a large part in calorie supply, but these are fairly rare geographically, and often seasonal in supply.

Other major changes to human diets have been the introduction of considerable processing ahead of the food entering the mouth. Thus we have cutting and grinding, cooking and many types of fermentation (such as breads, beers, pickling and souring) to increase digestibility. We also have a range of storage options to circumvent seasonal shortages. Modern breeding has also produced foods that are far more concentrated in sugars and starches than were previously available. In addition, agronomic and processing technologies have allowed a relatively recent replacement of animal fats

with fats from plant sources, primarily polyunsaturated seed oils rich in Ω -6 (Ailhaud et al. 2006). Combined, these methods provide humans with a year-round supply of calories.

However, in spite of these food sources and pre-consumption processing, the role of gut fermentation as a source of saturated fats remains important for energy homeostasis and gut health. Indeed, selection of fermentation substrates may influence the proportions of SCFAs produced, with potentially variable gut health effects (Yue et al. 2021). Fortunately, although gut microbiota composition is remarkably stable through life, some degree of compositional modification can and does occur (Lozupone et al. 2012, Shang et al. 2018, Oliver et al. 2021, Gruneck et al. 2022).

It is well established that readily digested carbohydrate foods eaten to excess result in obesity of humans (Brillat-Savarin 1825, Banting 1864, Price 1939, Nishizawa et al. 1976, de Garine & Koppert 1991). As noted, the mechanism behind this obesity is more to do with dietary glucose and insulin response effects driving a calorie overload, largely indicated in the diet/insulin hypothesis, rather than the “eat less/move more” concept promoted in low-fat diets.

Despite these seemingly quite small individual differences, combined they clearly allow humans a relatively high-energy lifestyle. In addition, we have large periods of the day available for activities other than obtaining calories to maintain this lifestyle, and further, we have been able to adjust to living permanently in environments completely hostile to other apes.

So what has gone wrong and what can be done about it?

In essence, our modern Western diet has a large focus on readily accessible starch and/or sugar-based foods. These are highly palatable, and more so when also combined with fats (Lennerz & Lennerz 2018). Mammals appear to have no specific and direct sensing mechanism of dietary glucose sources, whether sugars or starches. It appears that humans do have a specific dietary fat sensing mechanism, but only for stearic acid, a C18:0 saturated fat (Senyilmaz-Tiebe et al. 2018). This highlights the potential for a further additive obesogenic effect from excess polyunsaturated fats (Yam et al. 1996, Simopoulos 1999, Ailhaud et al. 2006), driven largely by a mistaken heart-health hypothesis (Keys 1970, Ottoboni & Ottoboni 2004). Humans clearly have minimal direct calorie-sensing of proteins, since humans restricted to a largely protein diet have eaten them even to death. Proteins in plants are naturally relatively dilute and thus difficult to consume to excess, considering the sheer volume of material that would need to be ingested.

The bulk of modern calorie sources, primarily starches, sugars and polyunsaturated fats, are cheap because of the remarkable quantities that can be produced cheaply and efficiently, following advances in mechanisation, agronomy and processing (Thompson 1968). The danger is that we will continue to incorporate these components, even if fashionably plant-based (Willett et al. 2019), with a resultant continued increase in prevalence of obesity and related metabolic disorders. The anecdote of captive kangaroo rats doing poorly on their highly preferred food (lettuce) over rodent chow suggests the seasonal availability of leafy greens was important for the animals, but providing a “perpetual spring” diet was not of benefit (Power & Schulkin 2009 pp 102-104). In human terms, the modern high carbohydrate diet may be seen as a “perpetual autumn” of starch and sugar rich foods inducing

prolonged, or even chronic, hyperglycæmic periods and the resultant hyperlipidæmia, obesity and T2D. Somewhat similar examples abound with respect to animal obesity and diabetes such as domestic cats (Hoenig 2012, Verbrugghe & Hesta 2017), horses (Cameron et al. 2021), or primates in zoos (Diamond 2003).

If we are to take any message from our ancestral and deeper evolutionary past, it is:

- to consume a far higher proportion of fermentable components, whether plant or animal,
- to revise our fat intake to primarily saturated fats with an emphasis on stearic acid content,
- and to limit our glucose intake.

Conclusion

An evolutionary view of human diet, combined with modern diets and the current growing rate of obesity in our populations, indicates that a mismatch occurs between our diet and our health. This is not quite the same as the “thrifty gene” hypothesis, but reflects a more deep-seated issue of how our bodies work with regard to physiology and metabolism. The popular belief of glucose as the preferred source of energy is clearly a myth, but its continued existence perpetuates the view that sugars and starches are essential in our diet. These are undoubtedly valuable calorie sources but our insistence on eating primarily “perpetual autumn” foods is clearly not good for us. Our gut structure is modified towards absorbing a highly-nutritious but low-volume food, thus we cannot rely largely so much on fermentation of fibrous materials as the other great apes do, but rather have “outsourced” these functions to food selection and preparation. Increasing protein consumption to provide calories is physiologically dangerous. Rather than the calorie-dense but insulin-stimulating reaction to consuming sugars and starches, we would do better to focus primarily on calories ingested as saturated fats. The ketogenic diet is useful for specific circumstances, but a diet with the bulk of calories from fats will result in most metabolic energy needs being provided by derived ketones rather than by glucose.

Autoritätsdusel ist der größte Feind der Wahrheit. Einstein, 1901, per Google translate, *Authority fluff is the greatest enemy of truth.*

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